

3D4GREEN (Dr. J.Puszekiel)

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MSCR for Syngas+CO₂ conversion into valuable chemicals

Microchannel of 800-900 microns
Catalyst: 13.5Co-1Re-Alpha Alumina

Results under different operative conditions: > 80 % of C+5 selectivity and ~ 40 % conversion of syngas+CO₂ / ~50 % conversion of syngas

Waxes + liquids